

Melatonin for athletes

Irakli Chaganava^{1,2} - Associate Professor, PhD in chemistry (chaganava@irakli.info);

¹Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sport, Tbilisi, Georgia;

²Institute of Cybernetics of Georgian Technical University, Tbilisi, Georgia.

Keywords: melatonin, sleep, sports, health, rehabilitation, metabolism.

Abstract. This paper presents a review of melatonin applications studies carried out up to date by various research groups. The prior criterion for the selection of scientific investigations covered here is their relevance to the sport. The discussed substance has a relatively short pharmacological history, and its potential has not yet been fully explored. The scientifically proven effects of this substance on the human organism are presented. It is noted that in addition to hormonal, melatonin is responsible for other polyfunctional biochemical activities. Multiple investigations show the relationship between improved sleep quality and athletic performance. The results of the studies indicate that melatonin supplementation could have benefits beyond sleep. Such as, for example, interesting for sports to facilitate weight control, participation in anti-aging mechanisms etc.

Introduction. Melatonin is a hormone of the pineal gland that regulates the sleep-wake rhythm and has a wide range of additional effects. It is used in tablets or capsules to improve the quality of sleep. A positive effect on weight loss has been proven, as well as antioxidant and antitumor effects. Melatonin preparations first became available in the United States only in 1993, thus, this substance has a rather short pharmacological history, and its potential has not yet been fully explored.

Objectives. The aim of this study is to find out and substantiate the benefits of using melatonin for athletes.

Materials and methods. In this paper we present a review of the studies published up to date in the scientific literature on the applications of melatonin.

Results and discussions. Many of the effects of melatonin are due to interactions with the corresponding receptors (MT₁, MT₂), while other effects are related to its antioxidant effects where the particular importance has the ability of melatonin to preserve DNA. As a result of independent studies, researchers have repeatedly come to similar conclusions that melatonin helps to reduce oxidative stress after exercise, increases endurance, promotes the acceleration of recovery processes, improves performance, directly contributes to the normalization of sleep quality, and helps to eliminate problems with blood pressure arising from hormonal disorders,

together with this melatonin improves the psycho-emotional state of an individual. The greatest value to melatonin is given by athletes involved in powerlifting and bodybuilding.

Melatonin in sports. The results of the study indicate that melatonin supplementation could have positive effects beyond sleep. Melatonin is involved in the regulation of body weight, and there is evidence that it can reduce the proportion of body fat and prevent obesity (especially when combined with calcium) [1].

The supplements highlight Melatonin's ability to reduce post-exercise oxidative stress and improve recovery. Melatonin manifests the main role in sports in the form of accelerating adaptation to a change in the athlete's environment. Studies show the relationship between improved sleep quality and athletic performance. At the same time, it was confirmed that in excess it inhibits the sympathetic nervous system and worsens sports productivity [2].

Most interesting are the findings that aerobic exercise decreases the amount of melatonin produced by the organism. On the other hand, high-intensity exercise affects less melatonin secreted by the endocrine system, which subsequently does not lead to the abovementioned unwanted effects. Numerous reports regarding the risks of disrupting the biological circadian rhythms of athletes, especially as a result of long-distance avia travel, indicate that neither the use of medicated melatonin, nor exposure to bright light or other strategies taken alone are ineffective. Research results show that melatonin improves resynchronization of biological rhythms in athletes most effectively when combined with comprehensive measures that should include exercise and stay in good natural light during the day [2].

Despite the fact that melatonin is a hormone, occasional excess of its dose does not pose a health hazard. It should be noted that in rare cases, adverse reactions to melatonin are still possible, among which are: headache, manifestation of symptoms characteristic of allergies, the effect of oversleeping, nausea and a feeling of depression. There are conditions for an increase in the prolactin index. These effects stop after discontinuation of the drug. By assessing the health risk / benefit ratio, a general conclusion can be drawn about the much greater benefit of the intended use of melatonin.

Conclusions. Studies have shown that the synthetic hormone melatonin isn't harmful and fits well with a healthy lifestyle.

The use of melatonin is recommended for manifestations of insomnia, such as difficulty falling asleep or periodic night awakenings, as well as to prevent Jetlag syndrome when changing time zones.

Melatonin is able to correct endocrine imbalances causing metabolic disorders.

There is evidence that, when combined with calcium, melatonin is able to reduce the body/fat proportion by stimulating the formation of "beige fat".

References

1. Barrenetxe J, Delagrange P, Martínez J (2004). "Physiological and metabolic functions of melatonin". *J Physiol Biochem* 60 (1): 61–72.
2. López-Flores, Marcos & Nieto, Raúl & Moreira, Osvaldo & Suárez Iglesias, David & Villa, José. (2018). Effects of Melatonin on Sports Performance: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Exercise Physiology Online*. 21. 121-138.